

TEACHERS' CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES IN TEACHING READING: ITS INFLUENCE TO LEARNERS' READING PERFORMANCE

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Teachers' Challenges and Strategies in Teaching Reading: Its Influence to Learners' Reading Performance

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Abstract

In the purview of reading development, it is essential that the potential of every learner must be developed. Thus, the main thrust of this study was to determine whether the challenges of teachers' strategies in teaching reading during Covid-19 pandemic and the learners' level of reading performance are significant. The select teachers and their Grade 4 pupils in Dansolihon Elementary School, Division of Cagayan de Oro were the respondents. The mixed method of quantitative and qualitative was used to gather information on the challenges of teachers' strategies and learners' reading performance. A guided response and rating scale type of questionnaire was floated. Mean distribution measures the challenges, while the frequency percentage on the level of reading performance. Spearman rho and Pearson were used to get a significant relationship between the teachers' strategies, learning reading and the extent of reading performance. There were gaps in the implementation of such strategies considering that most of the pupils were not ready for the sudden change of their learning modality. Hence, this study established that the teacher respondents were effective in strategizing teaching reading but same it is not significant to the level of reading performance. Therefore, recommendations were raised such as developing a reading hub in every school, modifying reading materials that aligned to the learners' interest, innovate learning materials, parents should fully support reading development programs, and the future researchers to study the various online platforms that would help the learners improve their reading ability.

Keywords: *teachers' reading strategies, pandemic reading performance*

Introduction

There is a dramatic change in educational delivery and learning attitude as well as school performance of learners after the Covid-19 Pandemic which critically affect the pupils' learning engagements, literacy and numeracy performance, and psycho-social skills of the public school learners. Thence, educational experts and teachers introduce intervention strategies to address the reading challenges of pupils in the learning recovery program.

The framework of the study is anchored on the flagship of the DepEd "Every Child A Reader Program" (ECARP), through the D.M. 402, s. 2004 and A.O. 324, which highlight the goal of the government to enable every Filipino child to communicate in English and Filipino through effective reading instruction in the public basic education and D.O. 42, series of 2016 which directs teachers to follow the competencies set by DepEd as reflected in the budget of work. This entails managing their classes and lessons effectively and ensuring that learning outcomes are achieved. It means that lessons are not just covered as scheduled but are also understood.

Teachers are required to employ strategies to keep within the budget of work. Additionally, teachers keep within the budgeted lessons by means of strategies such as lesson study, advanced and/or remedial reading and giving of home works to prepare pupils for advance learning.

The Covid-19 pandemic has brought terrible effect to the educational sector not only in the Philippines but also to the whole world. As Roman, et al (2022) pointed out, the pandemic has significantly contributed to the declining quality in the schools' reading program and the reading competence of public school learners in the new learning recovery period. Additionally, it was accentuated that pupils had experienced difficulty in the new learning conditions which affected considerably their reading achievements and performance.

Fuentes, et al (2022) found out that pupils in the grade school were evaluated to have lack of foundational reading skills during the Covid-19 pandemic because the modular distance learning does not allow teachers to teach the fundamentals of reading directly to pupils which had the differential effect to pupils' reading performance.

Further, it was emphasized that there is reason to assume that Covid-19 pandemic had a differential effect on pupils' reading performance. Hence, Benjamin, et al (2022) reported that teachers are stimulated to adapt reading strategies which are more effective in developing pupils' reading and reading comprehension proficiency such as using pupils' existing knowledge to interpret texts in order to construct meaning.

It is based on the above-stated considerations that the researcher is stimulated to conduct this study to ascertain pupils' reading performance after the Covid-19 Pandemic and present most effective reading strategies to address the challenges on reduced reading performance of pupils in Dansolihon Elementary School in the City of Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2022-2023.

Research Questions

The study aims to ascertain the effect of Covid-19 Pandemic to reading performance of fourth grade pupils of Dansolihon Elementary

School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro for the School year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the challenges in teaching and learning reading during the Covid-19 Pandemic?
2. What is the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading in Dansolihon Elementary School?
3. What is the level of pupils' reading performance when they are categorized as:
 - 3.1. independent;
 - 3.2. instructional; and
 - 3.3. frustration?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges in teaching and learning reading during the Covid-19 Pandemic?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading and pupils' reading performance?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of survey questionnaires, interview, and focused-group discussion (FGD).

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the Grade 4 teachers and pupils of Dansolihon Elementary School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

There were forty (40) pupils whose reading performance were assessed, evaluated, and utilized in the study. The respondents were chosen purposively for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The study is adapted from Roman, et al (2022) who asserted that pupils' difficulty in reading in the new learning recovery period was the result of the modular distance learning because pupils do not have the self-regulatory skills to read and teachers do not directly teach reading which had the differential effect to pupils' reading performance.

The research instrument is composed of three (3) major components. The first component is on the challenges in teaching and learning reading during the pandemic with ten (10) indicators. Additionally, the second component of the research instrument is on teachers' strategies in teaching reading in the learning recovery period with ten (10) indicators. Third component of the research instrument is on pupils' reading performance categorized as independent, instructional, and frustration.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission was asked by the researcher to the parents of the pupil-respondents to allow their children to participate in the study and to use pupils' reading performance as variable of this study. Moreover, the parents assured that the data gathered was treated to its highest confidentiality and be used for research purposes only. After the observation of pupil-respondents and interview, the researcher summarized and tabulated the data and submit to the Statistician for analysis using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the challenges in teaching and learning reading during the pandemic.

For Problem 2, mean and standard deviation were used to ascertain the teachers' strategies in teaching reading.

For Problem 3, Frequency and percentages were used to present the pupils' reading performance.

For Problem 4, Pearson r was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the challenges in teaching and learning reading during the Covid-19 Pandemic and pupils reading performance.

For Problem 5, Pearson was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the teachers' strategies in teaching reading and the pupils' reading performance.

Results and Discussion

This section includes the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from this study. Presentation of data is based on the classification of the problems presented in this study.

Problem 1: What are the challenges in teaching and learning reading during the Covid-19 pandemic?

Teaching and learning reading are the competencies that need to be materialized amid the challenging time brought by Covid-19 insofar as education and reading comprehension of the students. Table 1.1 presents the mean distribution on challenges in teaching and learning reading.

Table 1. *Distribution on Challenges in Teaching and Learning Reading*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1) The teacher provides self-directed learning materials in reading during the pandemic.	4.93	.325	Always
2) Provides limited in-person discussion during pandemic	4.79	.518	Always
3) Provides word-level skills where pupils identify the words and define them in the3 distance learning materials	4.60	.681	Always
4) Provides word-story lines in the distance learning materials for easy understanding	4.44	.700	Most of the Time
5) Provides different reading comprehension materials based on pupils' learning preference	4.18	.857	Most of the Time
6) Provides both print and non-print reading activities such as videos with translation	3.87	.928	Most of the Time
7) Provides differentiated reading activities and reading techniques for pupils' inclusive needs	3.31	1.001	Sometimes
8) Provides background knowledge activation activity	2.78	1.000	Sometimes
9) Provides questioning techniques to activate mental processes in distance learning materials	2.00	1.034	Seldom
10) Provides online/virtual or audio call to assess reading performance	1.55	1.018	Seldom
Overall	3.65	.806	Most of the Time

Legend: 4.50-5.00= Always/3.50-4.49=Most of the Time/2.50-3.49= Sometimes/1.50-2.49= Seldom/= 1.00-1.49= Never

Table 1.1 shows the mean distribution on challenges in teaching and learning reading. Overall, the respondents rated "Most of the Time" with a mean of 3.65 (SD- 0.806). This result implies that the challenges with respect to application of teaching strategies is highly observed. This means that amid the extraordinary situation brought by Covid-19, still the teachers could be able to adopt mechanisms to pursue teaching reading. Thus, it is of best suggestion to enhance other teaching strategies that fix in both online and offline learning. Teachers need to implement the various reading strategies particularly for both online and offline classroom and introduce some new digital application for reading (Anggeraini, Episiasi & Sulisty, 2022).

The indicator, "The teacher provides self-directed learning materials in reading during the pandemic," obtained the highest mean of 4.93 (SD= 0.325) which verbally described as "Always." This result signifies that amid the inconvenience brought by the pandemic, it is very highly observed that providing learning resources to foster reading ability of the pupils is materialized. Hence, the teachers should properly implement such strategies through improving their pedagogical knowledge and enhancing inquiry-based learning. Davis (2024) posits that inquiry-based learning is one of the most powerful teaching strategies in the classroom because research tells the teachers that students learn best when they construct their own meaning. Further, Davis added that inquiry-based learning triggers student curiosity.

Upon the other hand, the lowest mean of 1.55 (SD= 1.018) is verbally described as "Seldom" in the indicator, "Provides online/virtual or audio call to assess reading performance." This result explains that due to pandemic, implementation towards the technology integration in reading such as online or virtual is slightly observed. This indicates that amid the extraordinary times, still only few of the students have better access to technology. Hence, it is of best recommendations that the school should enhance innovative teaching-learning to improve the reading ability of the learners. Oktarina (2018) opines that the teacher should put them in position to experience the power of reading by the use of innovation.

Problem 2: What is the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading in Dansolihon Elementary School?

The strategies in teaching reading delve into a situation where the students have engaged the learning activities which created for that purpose. These strategies may be implemented indirectly to foster the reading skills of the learners. Table 2 presents the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading in Dansolihon Elementary School.

Table 2 presents the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading in Dansolihon Elementary School. Overall, the respondents verbally described as "Most of the Time" with a total mean of 4.40 (SD= 0.673). This result indicates that the application of teachers' strategies in teaching reading is high. This further characterizes that due to the demand of distance learning, teachers opt to strategize

their modality in teaching. Conversely, it is important that the teachers should continue enhancing pedagogical knowledge through continuing professional development through attending webinars, seminars or other similarly situated event that improve both technical and pedagogical skills. Engage learning will be initiating professional development workshops on reading strategies (Singh, 2019). Moreover, Singh believed that professional development workshops help the teachers learn to teach children to read and understand the content.

Table 2. *Distribution of Teachers' Strategies in Teaching Reading*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1) The teacher utilizes the phonics (unit of sounds) approach in reading activities and exercises.	4.96	.196	Always
2) The teacher utilizes the "Read-Aloud" strategy in reading activities and exercises.	4.97	.171	Always
3) The teacher utilizes the graphic K-W-L chart in reading activities and exercises.	4.95	.219	Always
4) The teacher utilizes the graphic organizer in reading activities and exercises.	4.89	.314	Always
5) The teacher utilizes vocabulary instruction in reading activities and exercises.	4.73	.600	Always
6) The teacher utilizes the "reading-writing to learn" strategy in reading activities and exercises.	4.52	.703	Always
7) The teacher utilizes the structured-note taking strategy in teaching reading.	4.21	.782	Most of the Time
8) The teacher encourages pupils to actively involved in reading activities and exercises.	3.72	1.092	Most of the Time
9) The teacher encourages pupils to comprehend the text by analyzing and interpreting them.	3.57	1.233	Most of the Time
10) The teacher encourages pupils to read independently in school and at home.	3.50	1.417	Most of the Time
Overall	4.40	.673	Most of the Time

Legend: 4.50-5.00= Always/3.50-4.49=Most of the Time/2.50-3.49= Sometimes/1.50-2.49= Seldom/= 1.00-1.49= Never

Further, the indicator, "The teacher utilizes the "Read-Aloud" strategy in reading activities and exercises," obtained the mean of 4.97 (SD= 0.171) which verbally described as "Always." This result implies that the teachers' strategies in teaching reading is very high. This is true in the event that strategizing is of the essence due to pandemic. Thus, it is suggested that teachers should improve their innovative skills in teaching reading, aside from investing technology that would scaffold the learners' reading ability. In Spidell and Latty's (2018) study found that an innovative reading program, particularly for beginning readers, provides a research-based curriculum that teaches sounds and sight words systematically and joyfully.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.50 (SD= 1.417) verbally described as "Most of the Time" in the indicator, "The teacher encourages pupils to read independently in school and at home." This result implies that the application of teachers' strategies through motivating the pupils to read independently is high. This is true in a situation where the students really need enforcement to improve their reading ability. Similarly, this suggests that the teachers should improve motivational skills in teaching reading. The fundamental aim of effective use of teacher's motivational skills is to stimulate and facilitate any learning activity (Tobgay, 2021). Interestingly, Tobgay added that it is important for the teachers to do a lot with student's motivational learning as an effective form of learning.

Problem 3: What is the level of pupils' reading performance when they are categorized as: Independent, Instructional, and Frustration?

Reading performance of the pupils is characterized as an accomplished task with respect to their reading competency, along with the activation of their reading skills and comprehension. This performance is being measured through standardized tool created for that purpose. Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupils' level on their reading performance.

Table 3. *Frequency Distribution of Pupils' Reading Performance*

<i>Level of Pupils' Reading Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Independent	20	20%
Instructional	55	55%
Frustration	25	25%
Total	100	100%

Table 3.1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of pupils' reading performance. It can be gleaned that 55 (55%) respondents obtained an instructional level of reading performance. This result signifies that among the pupil respondents, more than half of them have adequate background knowledge for a topic and can access text quickly with no or few errors. Interestingly, this result also indicates that most of the pupils in Dansolihon Elementary School are instructional readers. Thus, teachers and other stakeholders are encouraged to support any related reading development programs. Reading coordinators are also advised to improve their technical and other pedagogical skills to scaffold some learners who still have difficulty in reading and implement more student-centered strategies. Classroom teachers can combat this trend by applying an array of reading strategies and giving the students more of student-centered interventions from early grades (Alma & Evan, 2014).

Upon the other hand, among the respondents, only 20 (20%) were rated as independent readers. This result implies that though most of the students in Dansolihon Elementary School are readers, only few of them are considered excellent in reading. This further signifies that the school really need more reading intervention program and the stakeholders including the parents are suggested to support the learners by implementing positive reinforcement. Morin (2022) believes that positive reinforcement can be one of the most effective behavior modification techniques parents can use. Correspondingly, Morin added that positive reinforcement can encourage prosocial

behaviors, like sharing or following directions.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the challenges in teaching and learning reading during the Covid-19 pandemic?

Teaching and learning reading are characterized as essential component in the learning ability of the students, particularly during Covid-19 pandemic. The aforesaid component is being assessed through intervention and meaningful strategies that the teachers should implement. Table 4 displays the test of relationship between the challenges in teaching and learning during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Table 4. *Test of Relationship between the Challenges in Teaching and Learning during Covid-19 Pandemic*

<i>Challenges in Teaching and Learning Reading</i>			
(r)	p-Value	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
.142	.160	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted

**significant at p<0.05 alpha level*

Table 4 exhibits the results of the test of relationship between the challenges in teaching and learning during Covid-19 pandemic. Result shows that the teachers' strategies in teaching reading denotes "Negligible Correlation" to the extent of challenges in teaching and learning ($r = .142$) as the probability value ($p = .160$) means not significant. This result implies that the teachers' strategies do not necessarily reflect the level of challenges in teaching and learning during pandemic. This is probably true in a situation where most students are more curious the impact of pandemic rather than learning reading. Hence, it is encouraged that teachers and other stakeholders of education should establish effective teaching and learning style in guiding the learners achieve their level of competence amid the challenges. One of the strategies is using context clues. Kampen (2022) opines that strategy using context clue would help the learners determine the meaning of unfamiliar words. Moreover, the reading comprehension process is over before it begins if students do not have solid vocabulary knowledge or the ability to learn new words.

Henceforth, result indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted since the teachers' strategies and the challenges faced by the students during pandemic is not significant.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading and pupils' reading performance?

Teaching student to read during pandemic is one of the essential mechanisms to maintain competitiveness with regards to reading skills and comprehension. As such, teachers' strategies are in placed along with the proper assessment of the pupils' reading ability. Table 5 displays the results of the test of relationship between the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading and pupils' reading performance.

Table 5. *Test of Relationship between the Extent of Teachers' Strategies in Teaching Reading and Pupils' Reading Performance*

<i>Teachers' Strategies in Teaching Reading</i>			
(rs)	Sig. (2-Tailed)	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
.075	.458	Denotes Negligible Relationship	Accepted

**significant at p<0.05 alpha level*

Table 5.1 displays the results of the test of relationship between the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading and pupils' reading performance. It can be gleaned that that the level of pupils' reading performance denotes "Negligible Relationship" to the extent of teachers' strategies in teaching reading ($rs = .075$) with Sig (2-Tailed= .458) means not significant. This result indicates that the teachers' strategies in teaching reading during pandemic do not have significant relationship to the level of reading performance of the students. This means that there are other factors that can be considered helpful to improve reading abilities of the students aside from the existing modality of the teachers during those (extraordinary) times. Thus, it is suggested to modify other learning resources including but not limited in providing books, reading materials, and other innovations.

Accordingly, language learning process is still dominated by the use of printed teaching materials (Ramadhan, Atmazaki, Indriyani & Sukma, 2022). Ramadhan, et.al added that despite the fact the current learning process has been conducted in a variety of ways, such as online learning, blended learning, and hybrid learning, there is still a need to improve printed teaching materials to meet the expectations and achievements of students at this time. Henceforth, based on the results, this study indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings, this present study concludes the following:

Amid the extraordinary situation brought by the Covid-19, the teachers of Dansolihon Elementary School are challenged in adapting proper mechanisms in teaching reading. Notwithstanding the challenges, the teachers provided learning resources to ensure the reading ability of their pupils. This concludes further that due to pandemic, only few of the students have better access to technology.

This study concludes that due to pandemic, the teachers in Dansolihon Elementary School opted to strategize their teaching including

modification of topics and their modalities. Moreover, it is concluded that strategizing is materialized during pandemic. Hence, through motivation, students were fond in reading but still most of them need to have positive reinforcement.

Interestingly, some pupils have adequate background knowledge for a topic and could easily access text with few errors. However, this concludes that there were some pupils need to be guided in reading.

Further, the strategies of Grade 4 pupils in Dansolihon Elementary School do not necessarily reflect the level of challenges because it is observed that more students were curious the impact of pandemic rather than of learning reading.

Corollary, the teachers' strategies in teaching reading during pandemic do not have significant effect as to the level of reading performance since it is observed that there are still other factors to be considered.

Based on the findings, the study came up with the recommendations that could help the stakeholders improve the learners' reading performance:

The Department of Education (DepEd) should develop a reading program that fixes some gaps in the implementation of online and offline learning. Investing to develop reading hub in every school is recommended.

School principals and school administrators should create a special committee to modify reading and learning resources that best suited to their clients. It is recommended to innovate learning materials.

Teachers should continue enhancing pedagogical knowledge through continuing professional development. Attending workshops, seminars, and other related event is recommended.

Parents as stakeholders of education are recommended to give their full support in the implementation of reading development programs including improving reading hubs with sufficient reading materials.

For the future researchers, it is recommended to study the various online platforms that would help the learners improve their reading ability. Aside from revisiting other related studies on reading, it is recommended that future researchers should consider also environmental factors in assessing the reading competency of the students.

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